

Microplastics and Nanoplastics: Exploring Neurotoxicity, Blood-Brain Barrier Permeation, and Cell Death

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Abstract

- Microplastics and nanoplastics, the byproducts of plastic degradation, have become an environmental and critical health concern.
- They are small enough to cross biological barriers, including the blood-brain barrier (BBB), and interact with neural cells, leading to neurotoxicity. Understanding these mechanisms is vital for comprehending the impact of micro- and nanoplastics on neurological health and developing mitigation strategies.
- This poster explores the etiology, pathophysiology, and epidemiology of nanoplastics' impact on neurotoxicity, BBB integrity, and cell death. Understanding these mechanisms is crucial for developing strategies to mitigate micro- and nanoplastic-induced neurotoxicity.

Introduction

Plastic pollution has become a global crisis, with approximately 5.25 trillion pieces of plastic debris in the oceans. As plastics degrade, they break down into smaller particles called microplastics and nanoplastics, which are less than 1000 nanometers in size. Nanoplastics are now found ubiquitously in the environment, including in drinking water, air, and food sources. Human exposure occurs through various routes, including ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact. Many noteworthy concerns are being raised about the potential health effects of micro- and nano-plastics once in the body, as they can interact with biological systems, including neural tissues, raising concerns about neurotoxic effects. Micro- and nanoplastics have recently been found in the blood of adult humans. A very concerning discovery is the presence of micro- and nanoplastics have been found in human placental tissue and fetal meconium. In figure 1 we can see characterization of micro- and nanoplastic particles by scanning electron microscopy.

Etiology

Nanoplastics are primarily formed through the degradation of larger plastic debris by environmental factors such as UV radiation, mechanical stress, and microbial activity. Fragmentation results in nanoplastics entering ecosystems via water bodies, air, and soil. Human exposure occurs through contaminated food and water sources, leading to nanoplastic accumulation in tissues..

Pathophysiology

Nanoplastics can enter the body through ingestion, inhalation, or dermal exposure. Once inside the body, nanoplastics can cross biological barriers, including the BBB, attributed to their small size and physical surface properties. This, in turn, leads to direct interaction with neural cells, triggering a cascade of events that contribute to neurotoxicity. One key mechanism of nanoplastic-induced neurotoxicity is the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Nanoplastics can induce oxidative stress in neural cells, leading to damage to proteins, lipids, and DNA. This oxidative damage can disrupt cellular function and contribute to neuronal cell death. Nanoplastics can also disrupt intracellular calcium signaling, leading to excessive calcium influx and activation of cell death pathways. This disruption in calcium homeostasis can lead to neuronal cell death and neurodegenerative diseases. In Figure 2 an Illustration depicting the overview of the neurotoxic effects of micro- and nanoplastics are seen. Figure 4 shows a schematic diagram illustrating potential cellular mechanisms of micro- and nanoplastic toxicity

Figure 1: Characterization of micro- and nanoplastic particles by scanning electron microscopy

Epidemiology

Currently, research on the epidemiology of micro- and nanoplastic exposure and neurotoxicity is still in its early stages. Animal studies have shown that exposure to nanoplastics can lead to neurobehavioral changes, neuroinflammation, and neuronal cell death. Human epidemiological studies are needed to correlate nanoplastic exposure levels with neurological disorders incidence.

Figure 2: Illustration depicting Overview of the neurotoxic effects of micro- and nanoplastics

Figure 4: A schematic diagram illustrating potential (speculative at the moment) cellular mechanisms of micro- and nanoplastic toxicity

Figure 3: Impact of micro- and nanoplastic exposure on the gut-brain axis

Discussion and Conclusions

- The impact of micro- and nanoplastics on neurological health is a complex and multifaceted issue.
- Figure 3 shows the impact of micro- and nanoplastic exposure on the gut-brain axis.
- While the exact mechanisms underlying micro- and nanoplastic-induced neurotoxicity are still being elucidated, current evidence suggests that they can have detrimental effects on neural cells and the BBB.
- Oxidative stress, calcium dysregulation, and inflammation are pivotal in nanoplastic-induced neurotoxicity. However, understanding long-term effects on neurological health requires comprehensive epidemiological studies.
- Strategies to mitigate micro- and nanoplastic exposure and protect neurological health necessitate interdisciplinary collaboration and regulatory interventions.

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